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AN APPRAISAL OF THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY IN NIGERIA: INTERNET & EMERGING ISSUES

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Abstract

The advent of globalization and technological innovations has made cyberspace a most complex place. The cyberspace itself is without boundaries and therefore its contents are not subjected to a single legislation, there is no universal intellectual property law. Intellectual property law is a branch of substantive law which compensates for creative effort and innovations by all creators. It guarantees ventures exclusive rights or some sort of temporary monopoly to exploit their works and inventions for a period with the backing of legal enforcement mechanism and subsequent disclosure to the public domain. On the other hand, intellectual property is an intangible creation of the human mind usually expressed or translated into tangible form that is assigned certain rights. The aims and objective of this paper is to determine the emerging legal issues arising from the use of the internet and other new social media platforms to determine whether the intellectual property rights are duly protected by law. The legal framework as well as the instructional frame work in the area of intellectual property is also considered. The paper examined the legal frame work and discovered that there is a lacuna in the area of internet regulations as related to intellectual property. The paper adopts both doctrinal and non-doctrinal research methodology being an arm-chair legal research. The paper finally gave some

recommendations which includes, but not limited to the followings; new systems and laws must be created to prevent people from taking and using protected contents, including search engine procedure and for internet users to always clearly identify their content source, either with a copyright notice or erroneously indicators, E-commerce company should ensure employees do not gain access to or keep in their possession any unauthentic copies of software and finally intellectual property right owners should utilize technological skills to protect their contents on the internet through the use of electronic copyright management system.

Keywords: Intellectual Property, Internet, Cyberspace, Globalization.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The advent of globalization and technological innovations has made the cyberspace a more complex place. The cyberspace itself is without boundaries and therefore its contents are not subjected to a single law; there is no universal intellectual property law. To appreciate this topic, it is essential to note and explain some terms and concepts in Intellectual Property (IP) Law and the rights derivable therefrom.

Intellectual Property Law therefore is a branch of substantive law, which compensate for creative efforts and innovations by allowing creators and inventors exclusive right or sort of temporary monopoly to exploit their works and inventions for a particular period with the backing of legal enforcement mechanism and subsequent disclosure to the public domain for the 'common wheel'.¹

Intellectual Property on the other hand is an intangible creation of the human mind, usually expressed or translated into a tangible form that is assigned certain rights to the property. It represents knowledge, creative ideas or expressions of the human mind that have commercial value and are protected under patents, trademarks, copyright or trade secret laws from imitation, infringement and dilution. It belongs to a unique class of property rights that are not physical in nature but exist in the ephemeral. The uniqueness of intellectual property is that it is concerned with the protection of the works that are a result of hard work, talent, ingenuity, and sheer brilliance. The idea is to reward persons who exhibit these traits and produce such works whilst discouraging the lazy, indolent and un-resourceful persons.²

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are rights conferred by statutes on an individual or a corporate body with respect to the product of his or her intellect, guaranteeing the

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¹K.J. Joseph. 'Intellectual property Law and Entrepreneurship in Nigeria: Principles and practice'. (Aboki publishers, 2015) <http://www.book.google.com.>adouts-intellectualproperty-and-enterpneuership> accessed on 25th August, 2022.

²Ibid at p. 13

exclusive control of his work for a limited period. The object of protection here is usually 'a work of the mind or human intellect'³. IPR deals with legal reliefs enjoyed over the products of the mind which may result from the activities of persons in the industrial, scientific and artistic endeavour.⁴

The effort to protect and make sure that IPR holders derives some benefits from the fruits of their labour and gain some financial incentives from the work of their minds have, over the years become of concern to many IPR holders in both National and International spheres most especially with the advent of technology and social media platforms. The law therefore is intended to protect an IPR holder by giving him/her some level of control, management and use of his creativity for a certain period of time.

Intellectual Property rights comes in different forms and they do enjoy protection through legal mechanisms as we intend to discuss in this paper and to also consider the emerging issues arising from the use of the Internet and other new and social media platforms. Our effort is to x-ray the challenges and enormous issues confronting the IP Law with the emergence of the Internet in the distribution, management and dissemination of information in this digital age and to recommend possible ways in addressing same.

1.1 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH ARTICLE ARE:

- i. To determine the emerging legal issues arising from the use of the internet and other new social media platforms under intellectual property law;
- ii. To determine whether the intellectual property rights are duly protected by law;
- iii. To examine the legal framework as well as the instructional framework in the area of intellectual property;
- iv. To proffer solutions to the emerging legal issues on the use of internet as part of intellectual property.

Therefore, this paper is aimed at examining the legal framework of intellectual property with view to discover limitations in the area of internet regulations as related to intellectual property. The paper adopts both doctrinal and non-doctrinal research methodology being an arm-chair legal research. The paper finally gave some recommendations.

³.Ibid at p. 33

⁴. *Ibid*.

1.2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Ikenga K.E Oraegbunam in his work examines critically the nature of the internet in relation to its facility for committing crimes.¹ He identifies the fact that the internet is open, user controlled, global, decentralized, in expensive, abundant, interactive and make up use of independent infrastructure. He notes that with the increasing overdependence on computer systems with the global internet, the incidence of cyber criminality is significantly on the rise yet investigation and prosecution of suspects are greatly hindered due to the nature of cyberspace which makes it difficult to identify suspects and their conducts. He equally observes a world difference exist between physical borders and cyberspace and that the structure of the internet diminishes the chances for enforcement of laws and regulations that are national in scope. He recommended that there is need for legislatures for the progress in science and technology.

Mena Ajapovi has made useful contributions under cyber law and trade mark. He examines the thin border of domain names and trademarks strictly from the Nigerian prospective². He identifies the body which supersizes⁵ the registration of domain names in Nigeria which is the internet corporation for assigned names and numbers (ICANN)³.

The corporation, as he maintained, wakes in concert with the World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO). He notes that Nigeria as part of the international community must keep pace with the global trends of business and our laws must be reflective to accommodate changes brought by technology development. He observes that our Intellectual Property Laws must be visited by the legislatures to accommodate the needed charges.

On international literatures that led credence to a regulating mechanism for ICT the book law and internet⁵ is very relevant in this regard.

On the impact of technology on the regulation of copyright, Michard Inyang observes that law follows and changes as technology advances and that the technology has influenced the copyrights laws globally. He observes that there is need for Nigeria to amend her

⁵ Ikenga K.E Oraegbunam; The internet and its facility for criminality; Some unique difficulties for investigation and prosecution (2014) Vol.5 Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence pp22-26.

existing copyright laws to address the innovation to copyright and distribution of copyrights works⁴.

On the internet Governance, Anthony Taubman observes that there are some regulatory issues thrown up by internet, closely connected to its technical character and its practical operation. The question of who should manage the essential backbone and architecture of the internet, in particular the Domain Name System (DNS), Generic Top Level Domains (GTLDs) and the allocation of Internet Protocol (IP) should be addressed⁶.

1.4 CLASSIFICATIONS OF INTELLECTUAL COPYRIGHTS

Basically, Intellectual Property covers two major areas namely;

- I. Copyright (otherwise known as IP); and
- II. Industrial Property.

Copyright deals primarily with literary, musical and artistic creation such as books, music, arts, films, and broadcast as well as life performance and expressions of folklore. Industrial Property on the other hand involves patents, trademarks, industrial designs, geographical indications and appellations of origins, utility models etcetera⁶.

2.0 LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY IN NIGERIA

The legal framework on Intellectual Property in Nigeria hinges on the Patent and Design Act, the Trademarks Act, the Copyright Act and Cybercrimes Act. The Institutional Frameworks under these Acts are Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCPC), National Office of the Technology Acquisition and Protection (NOTAP), National Information and Technology Development Agency (NITDA), National Film and Video Censors Board (NFVCB), National Broadcasting⁵ Commission (NBC), National Council for Arts and Culture (NCAC), National Copy Rights Commission (NCRC) and Trade Malpractice Investigation Panel (TMIP).

It suffices to note that Section 3, 4, 15 and 16 of the Patent and Design Act creates a registry which would oversee Patent and Designs. Likewise, Section 1 of the Trademark Act also establishes a registry administered by the registrar of Trademarks. Both the Registrar of Patents and Designs and Trademarks are appointed by the Federal Civil Service

⁶. J.K. Joseph op cit.

Commission. The Law Department of the Federal Ministry of Trade and investment supervises issues of Patents, industrial Designs and Trademarks in Nigeria. Also, Section 34 of the Copyright Act establishes the Nigerian Copyright Commission (NCC) and empowers it to administer and regulate copyrights in Nigeria.

Meanwhile, other institutions that exist, pursuant to other legislatives with mandate for the protection and development of intellectual property in Nigeria includes: the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCPC) established under the FCCPC Act, 2018; the National Office of the Technology Acquisition and Protection (NOTAP) established under the WETAP Act; the National Information and Technology Development Agency (NITDA) established by the NITDA Act; the National Film and Video Censors Board (NFVCB) established under the NFVCB Act; the Trade Malpractices Investigation Panel (TMIP) created under the Trade Malpractices (Miscellaneous Offences) Act; the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) created under NBC Act and the National Council for Arts and Culture (NCAC) established under the NCAC Act.

3.0 THE INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY IN NIGERIA

3.1 FEDERAL COMPETITION AND CONSUMER PROTECTION COMMISSION (FCCPC)

Section 17 of the Act provides for the functions of the FCCPC to include:

- (i) To initiate broad based policy and review economic activities in Nigeria to identify anti-competitive and anti-consumer protection and restrictive practices which may adversely affect the economic interest of consumers;
- (ii) To eliminate anti-competitive agreements, misleading, unfair, deceptive or unconscionable marketing, trading and business practices; regulate and seek ways for removing from the market hazardous goods and services and cause offenders to replace such goods and services with better alternatives; and
- (iii) To encourage trade, industry and professional associations to develop and enforce quality standards designed to safeguard consumers with their various fields including in the area of intellectual property.

3.2 NATIONAL OFFICE OF THE TECHNOLOGY ACQUISITION AND PROTECTION (NOTAP)

Section 4 of the NOTAP Act empowers NOTAP to encourage a more efficient process for the identification and selection of foreign technology, develop the negotiating skills of Nigeria

with the view to ensure the acquirement of the best contractual terms and conditions by Nigerian parties who enters into any contract for the transfer of foreign technology to Nigeria.

NOTAP is responsible for the registration of all contracts or agreements having ⁷effect in Nigerian parties. NOTAP also is empowered by law to monitor continuously the execution of any contract or agreement registered by NOTAP.

3.3 NATIONAL INFORMATION AND TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (NITDA) ACT

Section 6 of the NITDA Act, tasks NITDA to among other things create a framework for the planning, research, development, standardization, application, coordination, monitoring, evaluation and regulation of information technology practices, activities and systems in Nigeria, provide universal access for information technology and systems penetration in rural, urban and under-served areas, develop guidelines for the standardization technology escrow source code and object code domiciliation, application and delivery systems in Nigeria.

In pursuance to its statutory functions NITDA maintains and operates the gov.ng domain name in Nigeria. In this respect NITDA (in collaboration with Nigerian Internet Registration Association NIRA) is responsible for the registration of users (mainly Federal, State and Local Government agencies) of the domain name. It is also responsible, as a forum for first instance where parties cannot settle, for the resolution of dispute arising from the use of the domain name.

3.4 NATIONAL FILM AND VIDEO CENSORS BOARD (NFVCB), NATIONAL BROADCASTING COMMISSION (NBC), NATIONAL COUNCIL FOR ACTS AND CULTURE (NCAC) AND TRADE MALPRACTICES INVESTIGATION PANEL (TMIP).

Under Section 2 of the NFVCB Act, the NFVCB is empowered, among others to license persons to exhibit films and video works in Nigeria, license premises for the purposes of exhibiting films and video works in Nigeria, censor films and video works in Nigeria,

⁴ Micheal Inyang; The Impact of Technology on copy right (2014) Vol.8 University of Uyo Law Journal. Pp 160-176

⁵ L. Edwards & C. waelde (eds), Law and Internet (Third edition, Hart Publishing Ltd, Oxfend USA, 2009) pp 6-89

⁶ Anthony Tauban, International Governance and the internet in Edwards, L & Waelde, C (eds) Law and internet (supra)

regulate and prescribe safety precautions to be observed in licensed premises, and regulate and control cinematographic exhibits.

The National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) is empowered by section 2 of the NBC Act to regulate and control the Nigeria broadcast industry, undertake research and development in the broadcast industry, receive, process and consider application for the ownership of radio and television stations including cable television services, direct satellite broadcast and any other medium of broadcasting and to recommend applications through the minister to the president, for the grant of radio and television licenses. The NBC is also engaged to promote Nigerian culture, moral and community life through broadcasting.

Section 3 of the National Council for Arts and Culture (NCAC) Act, empowers the NCAC to promote and foster the appreciation, revival and development of Nigeria Arts and Culture, foster the development of literacy, visual and performing arts in Nigeria, assist the National Commission for Museums and Monuments (NCMM) in the creation, acquisition and preservation of art works, cultural monuments and depositories, organize and promote exhibition in visual, performing and literacy art, cinema, films, photography, folklore, oral tradition, literature, poetry, painting, sculpture, architecture, town planning and general arts, woodwork, embroidery, weaving and similar crafts.

3.5 TRADE MALPRACTICES INVESTIGATION PANEL (TMIP)

The Trade Malpractices Investigation Panel (TMIP) is established under Section 2 of the Trade Malpractices (Miscellaneous Offences) Act to investigate offences under the act and report same to the Attorney General of the Federation AGF for prosecution.

Section 1 of the Act provides for the offences under the Act to include labeling, packaging, selling, offering for sale or advertising of any product that is false or misleading or likely to create a wrong impression as to the character, quality, brand name, value, composition and merit or safety of the product.

It is worthy to note the power given by law to the institutions above to regulate intellectual property does not specifically capture activities done on the internet. For example, NBC, NFVCB, NCAC etc. the law that created them and empowered them did not make specific provisions for the regulations of placing of films, videos, operating TV stations and radio stations on the internet such as YouTube, Facebook and other social media platforms.

Therefore, there is urgent need for the amendments of these laws in order to regulate activities being done on the internet and social media platforms.

4.0 THE EFFECTS OF THE INTERNET ON INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The internet is defined by Wikipedia as the global system of interconnected computer networks that use the internet protocol suit (TCP/IP) to link devices worldwide. It can also be referred to as a large computer network that links together other smaller computer networks. It is a network that consists of private, public, academic, business and government networks of local to global scope, linked by a broad array of electronic, wireless, and optical networking technologies.⁸

The concept internet can also be classified as new media which includes websites, streaming, audio and videos, emails, DVD and CD-Rom media, internet telephony and mobile computing. It can also include the social media which uses the media for interaction and interface. All these are technologies that have evolved as the society evolves.

The Protection of Intellectual Property Rights, not just in Nigeria but in other developed countries like the U.S.A has gotten a bit more difficult as technology has advanced. The internet has opened doors to allow people to easily copy and reproduce materials without the author's permission. It is a common knowledge that protecting one's property is essential to ensuring only you are able to profit from what is rightfully yours. However, it can be difficult to stay up-to-date on the laws and on the risk because they both are constantly changing as technology evolves.

Accordingly, piracy, which is the unauthorized use and sales of one's intellectual property, is a common issue online and one that most threatens one's rights. Hence, IPRs enable people to benefit from their innovations and creative work, and to prevent others from copying or unfairly gaining from the inventor's creativity and investment. According to these rights, society provides an incentive for people and organizations to invest time, resources, and original thinking to develop innovative products and technologies and expand knowledge and culture.⁹

⁸. *www.en.m.wikipedia.org. accessed 22/5/2019*

⁹. *J.K. Joseph op cit.*

Social media sites also are a cause for concern because they make it very easy for people to post and share content that may not belong to them. The unauthorized production and distribution of Intellectual Property materials on the internet has and is still a menace and a serious headache to inventors who lose lots of benefits from such activities. Patents, trademarks and copyrights are all at risk on the internet.¹⁰

The advent of digital technologies has indeed changed the world and our life. In the time of digital technology, it has become possible to produce and disseminate copies of copyrighted works with a mouse click; this has increased the number of copyright violations as well as made IP rights enforcement more complex. Trademark owners got a new headache too now they have to secure web-monitoring for potential trademark infringements in domain names and on Internet websites, to keep track on availability of new domain zones and fight cybersquatting.¹¹

It is pertinent to note that it is illegal and violation of the law to illegally download or distribute any copyrighted music on the internet. Such acts are prohibited by various municipal and International laws or legislations. The unauthorized downloading of musical and art works in the internet will no doubt deny the original owner the right to remuneration as royalty. It hinders hard work and productivity in the area of knowledge development.

4.1 IP ISSUES AND THE DISTRIBUTION OF CONTENT ON THE INTERNET

In recent years, there has been much publicity about the unlawful distribution of intellectual property such as music, films, art, photos, scripts, and software (“content”) on the Internet. These unauthorized downloads often violate national laws on copyright. This is as a result of ease of downloading digital files. Unauthorized copying of content has been a major problem causing the loss fortune in revenue for the owners of these rights. Thus, it is important for E-Commerce businesses to protect their respective IP rights on the Internet. This can be done in a number of ways which we will see later in this paper.

¹⁰.Petersen & watts Law Group ‘The effects of internet on intellectual property rights’ (2017) <https://www.petersonwatts.com/blog/2017/03/the-effects-of-the-internet-on-intellectual-property-rights>. Accessed October, 2021.

¹¹. <https://www.expertguides.com/articles/intellectual-property-law-in-the-digital-society-challenges-and-opportunities/ARCPWTMM>

The Napster case in the United States put an international spotlight on unauthorized downloading of music files. The case, which resulted in the court issuing a permanent injunction preventing Napster from operating its file sharing system, was a “contributory infringement” case because the claim was that Napster facilitated illegal copying by users of the system, not that Napster copied the files itself. Other cases will continue to test the law in this area, and there may be different issues and different results in different jurisdictions, but the lesson of Napster is that it is important for an E-Commerce company to make sure it has a clear policy against unauthorized copying of files, or any actions that encourage or facilitate such copying.

4.2 IP INFRINGEMENTS ON THE INTERNET – SOME LEGAL CONSIDERATIONS

Intellectual Property Right is assuming increasing importance in every facet of life today beyond what it had been originally owing to new developments in modern science and technology as well as challenges arising from the competitive nature of international trade. The result is that nations are increasingly faced with new developments and challenges in the protection, management and enforcement of IPRs.¹² In Nigeria, IPRs is governed by the Copyrights Act, Cap. 68, LFN, 2004. Trademarks, Patents and Designs Act, Cap. 344, LFN, 2004.

The absence of territorial limits on the Internet, along with the scope it offers for anonymity, has opened the door to infringements of intellectual property (IP) rights that are new in both nature and scale. Tangible counterfeit or pirated goods of almost every category are traded or exploited online, be it through legitimate business platforms such as online auction-houses, or through websites which trumpet their illicit character. Massive amounts of copyright-protected content in digital form, including software, music, films, electronic games and text, are also distributed online without the copyright owners’ consent via dedicated websites or file-sharing networks.

The enforcement of IP rights with regard to such activities raises a number of legal questions. From an international perspective, the most comprehensive set of rules

¹². *A paper presented by MS. Carolen T. Owoseni titled: “New Developments and challenges in protection of IPRs, a Nigerian Perspective.” At the International conference on IP, the internet, electronic commerce and traditional knowledge, Bulgaria, by (WIPO) Accessed online on 22/5/2019*

relating to the enforcement of IP rights is contained in the 1994 *Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights* (TRIPS Agreement). While a number of standards set out by this instrument apply equally to the offline and the online dimension of IP enforcement, infringements carried out over the Internet pose some very specific obstacles to effective enforcement which are not addressed in the TRIPS Agreement or in any other global treaty. The remarks below highlight a few of such questions.

i. Whom to sue? – Identifying the infringer

The level of anonymity which the Internet affords to its users creates an immediate enforcement problem for IP rights holders, since identifying the infringer must be the first step in any enforcement action.

The information required to identify an online infringer can often be obtained from the respective Internet Service Provider (ISP), which is able to match the relevant Internet Protocol address of a computer used on a network with the individual subscriber. There are no harmonized rules at the international level as to whether an ISP is obliged to disclose a subscriber's identity or other related information. The TRIPS Agreement (Article 47) includes an optional provision which addresses the right of information in connection with civil proceedings. This, however, is limited to information which the infringer himself must disclose and does not extend to disclosure by third parties. Meanwhile, national laws differ in their approach.

Efforts have been made in different ways - in the context of new legislation and in a large number of court decisions - to balance such a right of information with conflicting interests, such as protecting the confidentiality of information sources or personal data. A European Union Directive (2004/48/EC of April 29, 2004) on the enforcement of IP rights may also help to harmonize the situation among EU countries, by establishing in principle this kind of right of information against certain third parties.

ii. Where to sue? – Private international law issues

Suing for online infringement of IP protected material often involves cross-territorial action. This raises questions as to jurisdictional competence, the applicable law and the eventual enforcement of a judgment in another country. Such questions all touch upon complex issues of private international law and procedure.

These issues are not entirely new. Private international law doctrines have long been developing around the globe, and it is not necessary to unravel all these principles. Nevertheless, there is a difference in both degree and nature when these concepts are applied to disputes in a global Internet environment. Would, for instance, the fact that allegedly infringing content was accessible online in a certain country be deemed enough to establish jurisdiction of a court in that country? Would such jurisdiction extend to determining compensation for the entire damage suffered - potentially in many other countries? If redress can be sought in multiple courts, how can "forum shopping" practices be dealt with, i.e. which allow a plaintiff to file his motion in the jurisdiction which would be most favorable? Case law has in recent years developed some standards for the application of private international law principles in the online environment. But different national or regional private international laws systems continue to coexist.

In the field of contractual business-to-business disputes, the work of The Hague Conference on Private International Law is worthy of note. In June 2005, after over a decade of negotiations, its Member States adopted the *Convention on Choice of Court Agreements*. This aims to give effect to party agreements designating a court to adjudicate exclusively upon an existing or future dispute. With some exceptions, disputes involving IP matters are covered by the scope of the Convention.

iii. The Risk of Being Sued Abroad

For businesses involved in e-commerce, compliance with the IP laws of the countries in which a company operates may no longer be sufficient to ensure the reliable management of legal risks. A company may diligently comply with the standards governing the use of IP-protected content on its own territory. Yet the moment that the content is used on/via the Internet, it becomes accessible in numerous places across the globe, in some of which its use may not be legitimate.

For instance, taking into account the territoriality of trademark rights, identical trademarks can legitimately be held in different countries by unrelated owners. Such coexistence, long-established in the physical world, is more problematic on the Internet where a trademark is potentially visible from anywhere in the world. To operate entirely

safely in such an environment, a company would have to comply with the highest standards of protection available on a global scale, hardly a practicable solution.

The risks have been highlighted as a major concern for e-commerce business in, for example, the 2004 *Global Internet Jurisdiction* survey, published by the International Chamber of Commerce and the American Bar Association. In practice, companies often refrain from interacting with jurisdictions which they consider to be "risk" jurisdictions by, for instance, trying to identify the physical location of a user through user-registration, or by tailoring their online presence to particular jurisdictions.

The WIPO *Joint Recommendation Concerning Provisions on the Protection of Marks, and Other Industrial Property Rights in Signs, on the Internet* proposes a possible way to alleviate the concerns regarding trademarks' conflicting with existing rights in other forums. The provisions address three main questions: When can use of a sign on the Internet be considered to have taken place in a particular country? Can those who own conflicting rights in identical or similar signs make use of these signs online, and if so, under which circumstances? And how can courts take account of the territorial basis of trademark rights when determining remedies?

The effective enforcement of IP rights on the Internet remains a complex affair. Developments at various levels are seeking to adapt existing enforcement mechanisms to the specific features of online infringements. But as yet, the often-diverse national approaches may make it difficult for rights holders to assess the risks and advantages related to a specific enforcement action. This continues to create uncertainty for businesses operating online, as well as for consumers.

iv. Case Study: Hotel Maritime

A hotel owner in Denmark, who held a registered trademark "Hotel Maritime" in Denmark, was using this sign on his hotel's webpage, as well as in the respective domain *www.hotelmartime.dk*. Meanwhile a German company was operating some 40 hotels in Germany under the name "Hotel MARITIM" and had registered this trademark in Germany. In a dispute, decided by the Federal Supreme Court of Germany in 2004, the German plaintiff argued that the Danish hotel owner was infringing his trademark rights by, *inter alia*, using the sign on the hotel webpage.

The court, much in line with the elements of the WIPO Joint Recommendation, reasoned that not every use of a sign on the Internet should be treated as taking place in a given country, even if it was accessible to Internet users based there. Only where the use of the trademark had a "commercial effect" in a country, could it be treated as having taken place in that country, and thus be possibly relevant for an infringement claim. On this basis, the court found for the Danish defendant, arguing that the hotel services he offered did not have enough commercial effect on the business activities of the plaintiff in Germany.¹³

5.0 SOME RECOMMENDED SOLUTIONS TO INFRINGEMENT OF IPRs ON THE INTERNET

The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO 2007) report pointed out clearly that 'the internet and other constantly evolving digital technologies have opened up exiting opportunities for business and for new modes of creativity, while at the same time presenting complex challenges for the evolution of copyright'¹⁴ Similarly, social media present a number of challenges to IP law that, prior to its propagation, has not been seen before. The same rules apply, the same legislations govern and the same common law rights exist for those who own IP. But the sheer volume of materials being published on the internet, the speed at which materials can be transmitted and the vast number of individuals who can be reached around the world creates challenges for owners of IPRs never known before. At the same time, this reality raises serious concerns for user of social media who can be exposed, unwittingly or otherwise to liability for breach of IP rights.¹⁵ These challenges have to be addressed and below are some recommendations to IPR owners and the business community/entrepreneurs:

- a) New systems and laws must be created, and existing law on intellectual property be amended to capture issues on internet and other social media platforms in order to prevent people from taking and using protected contents without authorisation, including search engine procedures that prevents searching of copyrighted materials. This will help a great deal in curbing unauthorised use and broadcast of intellectual works.

¹³. Heike Wollgast, *WIPO Enforcement and Special Projects Division*.

¹⁴. *WIPO, 2007 at p. 16*

¹⁵. Anthony O. Uche et al. in their article titled: *Intellectual property and the new Media: Issues and challenges*

- b) Internet users should always clearly identify their content, either with a copyright notice or some other indication of ownership. You may wish to simply tell users what they can and cannot do with their content. Businesses should also take steps in ensuring that they do not distribute or permit downloads of third party content that does not belong to them, they should also put programs in place to make sure that employees understand the company's policies in this regard.
- c) It is also important for E-Commerce companies to make sure that employees do not gain access to or keep in their possession or on their systems any unauthorized copies of software or other content. Companies should have a system of prevention, education and monitoring to make sure that employees are not knowingly or unknowingly using illegal copies of software.
- d) All employees should know about the company's policies against misuse of IP, and senior management should be responsible for reviewing company business practices on a regular basis to make sure that the policy is being followed. It is wise to assess situations in which a policy violation is found, to see if disciplinary action should be taken.
- e) IPR owners can utilize technological skills to protect their content on the Internet, for example, watermarking, encrypting or otherwise creating identification and tracking systems. Electronic Copyright Management Systems are being proposed by business consortia and individual companies who see these systems as a way to use technical means to control use of content.¹⁶

The recommendations above are not exhaustive as there may be other ways by which we can improve the cyberspace considering the porousness of the digital environment, the inadequacies and obsolete nature of some of our laws which needs immediate amendments and or repeal in order to guaranty the enjoyment of IPR by the owners for the period prescribed by law.

¹⁶. <https://www.expertguides.com/articles/intellectual-property-law-in-the-digital-society-challenges-and-opportunities/ARCPWTMM>

6.0 CONCLUSION

We examined the intricacies of the cyberspace and its effects on IPRs. We also explained the classifications of Intellectual Property and the legal complexities of the borderless environment of the internet. We concluded by recommending measures for preventing the infringement of IPRs.

In summary, technological innovations and the cyberspace have positive impacts on globalizations, however, they pose a risk to protection of IPRs. Thus, as technological innovations continue to evolve, it is important that mechanisms are put in place to ensure that the IPRs continue to be protected on the internet across borders.